

User test: Part 1 & 2

*Required

Welcome to our user test!

The user test is divided into three parts, and you will answer the first two using this form. Before continuing with Part 1, please read and approve the following consent form of the handling of your shared personal data.

What is this project about and why do you want me to participate?
This survey is about soundscapes that utilise sonification of climate data. You are asked to participate in order for us to collect information about how these soundscapes are perceived.
The aim is to investigate how soundscapes can be used to foster thoughts about climate change.

How is the study conducted?
Participation in this study consists of listening to sounds and evaluating them. An interview will also be conducted in the end. The estimated duration of the survey is 45 minutes.

Possible consequences and risks of participating in the study:
Research subjects will not be exposed to any risks.

What happens to my information/data?
Your replies will be registered using Google forms. We will store your replies to questions about your perceptual experiences when listening to sounds and demographic information (age, gender). No IP-address or geo-location data will be collected. The purpose of the collection of personal data is to investigate how sonifications are perceived in different user groups. We will also make an audio recording of an interview session for transcription.

Data will be processed on a legal basis with the research subject's explicit consent, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). You have the right to access the information about you that is collected in this survey free of charge and, if necessary, to get any errors corrected. You can also request that information about you is deleted and that the processing of your personal data is restricted. If you want to do so, please contact the person responsible for the project (Roberto Bresin) with your email address and telephone number.

GDPR
consent

Roberto Bresin is also responsible for ethical conduct and scientific integrity of the research and correct data handling, i.e. that the data of the participants are transferred and used in a secure setting, and that the use of the data is compliant with ethical and legal requirements. Your answers and your results will be processed so that unauthorized persons cannot get access to them. The results of the study will be published in scientific conferences/journals and be pseudonymised (i.e. can not be traced back to you).

What happens with my data?
The data may only be used in the way you have given your consent to. Roberto Bresin is responsible for data storage and data processing. You have the right to say no to the data being saved. If you agree to data being saved, you have the right to later withdraw (cancel) that consent. In that case, your data will be discarded. If you wish to withdraw consent, please contact Roberto Bresin.

How do I get information about the results of the study?
You are granted the freedom of access to your individual data and/or the summarized results of the study if you want to learn about the results (this is, however, not required or mandatory).

Insurance and compensation:
No compensation or insurance coverage is provided.

Participation is voluntary:
Participation is voluntary and you can choose to cancel your participation at any time.

If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Roberto Bresin at roberto@kth.se.

1. GDPR Consent *

Tick all that apply.

I accept the above terms and consent to having my information stored as described in the above text.

Personal Information

2. Please enter your personal experiment code (given by the person conducting the test). For instance: "A1" *

3. Please enter you age: *

4. Please specify your gender: *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

5. What is your nationality? *

6. Do you have any hearing impairments? If yes, please provide a brief description. If no, skip this question.

Please provide a rating for the following statements:

7. "I consider myself aware and knowledgeable concerning climate related issues." *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree						

8. "I consider myself aware as an active proponent for sustainability." *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree						

User test: Part 1

Instructions

In the following test you will answer multiple questions, with each question concerning the properties of a particular sound. When you're ready, you will listen to the sound and choose the answer that you perceive is the correct one. You're allowed to listen to the sound multiple times. There's no time limit to answer the question. After the question is answered you will continue onto the next question. You're not allowed to go back and change the answer of a previously answered question or listen to a sound of a previously answered question.

Let us know if you have any questions and when you're ready to begin the test!

User test: Part 1

Question 1

9. The following sound represents size. Listening to the sound, do you consider the size... *

Mark only one oval.

- Increasing
- Unchanged
- Decreasing

User test: Part 1

Question 2

10. The following sound represents temperature. Listening to the sound, do you consider the temperature... *

Mark only one oval.

- Decreasing
- Unchanged
- Increasing

User test: Part 1

Question 3

11. The following sound represents event rate (frequency of occurrence) and mass. Listening to the sound, do you consider the event rate and mass...

*

Mark only one oval.

- Increasing
- Unchanged
- Decreasing

User test: Part 1

Question 4

12. The following sound represents temperature. Listening to the sound, do you consider the temperature...

*

Mark only one oval.

- Unchanged
- Increasing
- Decreasing

User test: Part 1

Question 5

13. The following sound represents event rate (frequency of occurrence) and mass. Listening to the sound, do you consider the event rate and mass... *

Mark only one oval.

- Unchanged
 Decreasing
 Increasing

User test: Part 1

Question 6

14. The following sound represents size. Listening to the sound, do you consider the size... *

Mark only one oval.

- Decreasing
 Increasing
 Unchanged

User test: Part 2

Instructions

In the following test you will for each question listen to two different sounds and then be asked to pick the sound that you consider the least positive (alternative "1" being the first one played and alternative "2" being the second one played). You will be informed before each sound is played which sound it is (alternative "1" or "2"). You're allowed to listen to the sounds multiple times. When you have made your choice you will continue onto the next question. There's no time limit to answer the question. You're not allowed to go back and change the answer of a previously answered question or listen to the sounds of a previously answered question.

Let us know if you have any questions and when you're ready to begin the test!

User test: Part 2

Question 1

15. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

User test: Part 2

Question 2

16. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

User test: Part 2

Question 3

17. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

User test: Part 2

Question 4

18. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

User test: Part 2

Question 5

19. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

User test: Part 2

Question 6

20. Which of the following sounds do you consider the least positive? *

Mark only one oval.

1

2

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